

From Communication Practices to Academic Success: The Multilayered Impact of Active Learning Practices

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Abstract

This study aims to examine students' perceptions of active learning methods in higher education. A quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected through a questionnaire administered to 224 university students who participated on a voluntary basis. The questionnaire included items related to demographic characteristics as well as students' experiences with active learning, their academic performance, and perceived effects on everyday learning practices. Descriptive statistical methods were used to analyze the data. The findings indicate that the majority of students perceive active learning methods positively and associate them with academic achievement, motivation, and communication skills. Practices such as group work, discussions, and problem-solving activities were evaluated by students as elements that enhance participation in the learning process. However, some participants reported challenges related to time management, group dynamics, and limited opportunities for practical application. In addition, the need for more time and structured planning during the implementation of active learning activities was highlighted as a factor that may hinder adaptation for some students. Furthermore, participants pointed out that insufficient technological infrastructure and instructors' continued reliance on traditional teaching methods may negatively affect the effectiveness of active learning practices. Overall, while active learning methods are perceived as supportive of students' academic and personal development, the findings suggest that addressing structural and pedagogical limitations is necessary to enhance their effective implementation in higher education contexts.

Keywords: Active learning, academic achievement, student engagement, communication skills, educational methods.

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Introduction

Today's technological developments are also effective in the field of education, one of the most important processes of human life, and transform learning styles. This period of easier access to information brings about lasting effects on learning and teaching styles. While many new concepts have been introduced to the literature in this period, studies on the practices of obtaining and processing correct information are gaining momentum and traditional learning styles are changing. These studies, which aim to sustain learning processes more effectively, aim to make sense of the acquired knowledge. While traditional teacher-centered learning styles have a mono-centered structure aimed at transferring information directly from the teacher to the student, today's modern learning approaches have a structure that encourages the active participation of the student in the learning process. This orientation has increased the number of studies that can help students discover, analyze and apply knowledge and put it into practice more easily. In this direction, active learning approaches adopt a student-centered learning style by offering various opportunities to students and support the individual's practices such as critical thinking, problem solving and cooperation.

Active learning models make it possible for the student, who is seen as a passive receiver in traditional learning styles, to take an active role in education. In this process, techniques that will make a difference such as problem solving integrated with teamwork, discussion and simulations are used, and students are enabled to develop deep approaches to the subject they learn. Individuals who participate in learning processes gain experience in accessing and interpreting information, which enables them to become successful individuals in the academic field. Compared to traditional learning styles, there are many studies that conclude that active learning practices increase student achievement. In traditional learning styles, the student is a passive listener, always waiting for the information to be conveyed by someone else and therefore learning is superficial. Today, when traditional learning styles are transformed into "active learning" styles that require the active participation of students, the retention, transfer and use of this knowledge to daily life becomes easier as students access information with their own efforts. In this study, the effects of active learning methods on students' academic achievement, motivation, communication skills and participation in the learning process are discussed. In addition, the study comprehensively examines the transformation of student-oriented learning environments in educational dynamics and the advantages and disadvantages of these learning styles for students. In the study, various suggestions are presented for the benefit of active learning methods for students, and the process of integration of these methods into existing education systems is evaluated. In the literature section of the study, in line with the findings of previous studies on the subject, active learning models and their contributions to education are discussed, and the necessity of integrating new learning models into today's education system is emphasized.

Active Learning in Education: Effectiveness, Participation and Transformation

The development of active learning models in the field of education dates back to the early 20th century when Maria Montessorin advocated for students to have a say in their own learning processes and encouraged them to learn in line with their natural curiosity (Lillard, 2005). John Dewey (1938) also emphasized that learning is a process based on the student's access to knowledge through direct experience rather than passive transfer of information. However, the development and implementation of these approaches has gained momentum since the mid-1980s. In this period, De Charms (1985) strengthened the psychological basis of active learning by arguing that having control over one's own learning process increases intrinsic motivation. Since the 2000's, many empirical studies supporting active learning

approaches have been conducted in developed countries and large-scale government-sponsored projects have been initiated in this field (Bonwell & Eison, 1991; Prince, 2004). Recent rapid developments in the field of science and technology have greatly affected social life and contributed to the economic growth of developed countries. Today, developments in information technologies give birth to information societies and these societies follow the new developments emerging with technology and adapt them to their own societies. It is known that education has a very important place in the formation of an information society. According to Woolfolk (1993), the new educational and psychological understandings that have been effective in the field of education since the second half of the 20th century have been created by taking into account these individual differences since individuals have different characteristics from each other. In this period, it is seen that the influence of the Behaviorist learning-teaching approach, which does not take into account the human mind and expresses learning as an action-reaction bond, has decreased in the field of education. Instead, the cognitive understanding that takes individual differences into account in education is more preferred. According to this understanding, which states that learning should become an active mental process, how individuals learn concepts, how they solve problems, how they retain information and how they remember and forget this information become important in the learning process.

The changing world order brings with it the processes of adaptation of every institution and organization to this order, and the most effective adaptation process is expected from educational institutions. One of the main reasons for this is the effort to facilitate the rapid adaptation processes of individuals trained by these institutions according to their fields of expertise. When it comes to fields related to education, it is inevitable to produce strategies by considering many components together. In educational studies, which have become an academic research field, the effectiveness of learning processes comes to the fore. The traditional learning model generally has a teacher-centered structure and students are passive in the learning process (Prince, 2004). In this method, the teacher presents information directly, while students are obliged to listen, take notes and memorize this information. However, research shows that traditional teaching methods limit student participation and make learning superficial (Michael, 2006). Active learning methods provide effective results in areas where traditional teaching methods are insufficient. The concept of active learning, which is encountered in many institutions that are transforming in an effort to renew themselves today, was first put forward by Bonwell and Eison and in this learning style, students took an active role in learning processes. In this method, students are seen as individuals who play an active role in learning processes rather than being passive recipients of information (1991). Research has shown that active learning method develops cognitive skills such as analyzing, evaluating and applying the information presented instead of memorizing it (Michael, 2006). In addition, it has been observed that students' motivation and academic achievement increase in courses where active learning strategies are applied (Chi & Wylie, 2014). The main reason for this is that students are encouraged to think deeply by using methods such as problem solving, group work, discussions, simulations, brainstorming and case studies in the learning process (Freeman et al., 2014). The main differences between traditional learning and active learning are listed below:

Traditional Learning

Teacher-centered: Information transfer is one-way.

Active Learning

Student-centered: Students actively participate in the process.

Traditional Learning	Active Learning
Based on rote learning: Focuses on remembering information.	Based on in-depth learning: Analyzing and applying knowledge is important.
Students are passive recipients: Lectures are usually monologues.	The student is an active participant: Activities such as group work and problem solving are at the forefront.
Knowledge transfer depends on the teacher.	Student develops independent learning skills.
(Feedback is limited.)	Continuous feedback is received and students are evaluated in the process (Bonwell & Eison, 1991).

When we look at the differences between traditional learning and active learning, it is clear that traditional learning styles are aimed at transferring knowledge directly. In particular, the realization of evaluation through examinations brings about a decrease in success. Recent studies show that active learning methods also significantly improve students' communication skills. Active learning techniques such as group-based learning, peer teaching, in-class discussions and problem-based learning allow students to express themselves effectively (Brookfield & Preskill, 1999; Chi & Wylie, 2014; Freeman et al., 2014). These findings are in line with the survey data conducted within the scope of our study. The majority of Communication Faculty students stated that group discussions and collaborative activities helped them express themselves better and improve their listening comprehension skills. However, the contribution of active learning practices to communication skills is not limited to classroom interaction, but also provides students with competencies that will directly reflect on their professional lives in the future. Barrows (1986) problem-based learning model naturally increases communicative interaction by having students work in groups on problems related to real life. Research results also support the model. Students stated that they developed skills such as teamwork, making presentations and contributing to team decisions in active learning processes. However, some participants also mentioned that equal opportunities to speak in the group were not always provided and that the communication environment could become competitive at times. The general trend shows that active learning plays a role in supporting communication skills and makes students better equipped both academically and professionally (Johnson et al., 1998; Michael, 2006; Prince, 2004).

Active Learning Methods and Practices

The teaching methods used in education greatly affect the ways in which learners access, process and apply information. Today, traditional passive learning models are being abandoned and replaced by student-centered active learning techniques. Active learning adopts an approach that aims to develop students' critical thinking, problem solving and communication skills by encouraging their direct participation in the learning process. The learning model in question puts the student at the center of the learning process and reveals methods for the student to access information, analyze and apply the information they access. The basic principles of active learning can be listed as follows:

- **Student Centered Approach:** The teacher assumes a directive role by leaving the central position and the student is positioned as an active participant in the process.

- **Experience-Based Learning:** Students learn by applying and experiencing information instead of being directly exposed to it (Kolb, 1984).
- **Collaborative and Interactive Environment:** Students are encouraged to understand information in depth by interacting with their peers, through group work and discussions.
- **Inquiry and Critical Thinking:** Students are involved in the processes of questioning, analyzing and evaluating information rather than memorizing it (Freeman et al., 2014).
- **Feedback and Self-Assessment:** Students are encouraged to continuously review and self-assess their learning processes (Chi & Wylie, 2014).

Considering these principles, the learning process that takes place with the active participation of the student brings permanent learning while providing opportunities to experience knowledge. There are many methods and techniques used to support this method. These methods are applied to increase student participation in the lesson, improve comprehension and facilitate knowledge transfer. Some commonly used active learning techniques are as follows:

- **Team Work:** The teamwork method refers to a process that includes the solutions of problems/problems produced on a specified topic and supports the process of learning together. These activities facilitate social learning and, according to Johnson, Johnson and Smith (1998), support students' communication, cooperation and critical thinking. The exchange of information within the team deepens the student's solution-oriented thinking skills by gaining different perspectives.

- **Discussions:** Discussion-based learning requires students to exchange ideas on a topic and to support their ideas with evidence that supports their opinions. Brookfield and Preskill (1999) state that discussions improve students' self-expression skills, increase critical thinking and encourage active participation in lessons. In addition, discussions also help students to confront their prejudices and develop different ideas.

- **Problem Solving:** This method encourages students to develop a search for solutions to problems they may encounter. Barrows (1986) sees problem-based learning as a method to encourage students to actively participate in research, to encourage independent thinking and to increase motivation in the learning process. Although this method is widely applied in disciplines such as science and business administration, it is a useful method that can also be utilized in social sciences.

- **Simulations and Role Play:** With the emphasis on visual learning today, simulations enable students to learn by experiencing the situation/process. This technique, especially used in medical, aviation and business education, allows students to practice by observing scenarios. Gredler (2004) states that simulations support experiential learning processes and help students cope with difficult situations.

These methods increase the student's interest in the lesson, contribute to active participation and bring permanent knowledge. According to Michael (2006), active learning methods lead to higher academic achievement, stronger motivation and increased critical thinking skills. Some of the main developments that reveal the dominant role of active learning methods in education can be listed as follows:

- **Integration of Technology:** Innovations such as online learning platforms, virtual classrooms and augmented reality are becoming tools that support active learning (Laurillard, 2012).

- **Increased Student Engagement:** Active learning makes the learning process meaningful by enabling students to become active participants rather than recipients of information (Prince, 2004).

- **Preparation for the World of Work:** Employers prefer individuals with critical thinking, collaboration and problem solving skills in their teams. Active learning contributes to students becoming well-equipped individuals in business life (Ramsden, 2003).

As in every field, rapid technological progress necessitates changes in the education system. Active learning methods, which aim for student-centered learning, offer content that can produce positive results to meet this need. It is clear that these methods, which bring with them the ability to analyze and interpret information and develop solutions for its successful practical use, will positively affect student achievement.

However, although active learning methods increase student participation, critical thinking skills and academic achievement, they also have some disadvantages. Compared to traditional methods, active learning practices require more time and limited time situations may lead to a decrease in content intensity (Prince, 2004). In addition, not all students can adapt equally to group work, and introverted individuals have difficulty in these processes (Michael, 2006). Again, compared to traditional forms of learning, active learning practices require a longer preparation process and require development in planning and classroom management skills (Bonwell & Eison, 1991). The changing role of the instructor may cause resistance from instructors and hinder active learning processes (Freeman et al., 2014). The inclusion of the active use of technological tools in educational processes causes technical infrastructure problems and deficiencies and negatively affects the process (Laurillard, 2012). For these reasons, in addition to the potential benefits of active learning, the limitations that may be encountered in the implementation processes should also be taken into account.

Methodology

Quantitative research method was used in the study to examine students' perceptions of active learning methods in relation to their academic achievement, motivation, and communication skills.. The ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University Ethics Commission. The study proposal was reviewed at the commission meeting dated 27.11.2024 (Decision No: 12) and approved with the ethical clearance code 2024/412. Data were collected voluntarily in the study. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended/open-ended questions evaluating students' demographic information, active learning experiences, and the impact of these processes on their academic and personal development. Participants were clearly informed that they had the right to withdraw from the study at every stage of the study. In the study conducted in accordance with ethical rules, written consent was obtained from the students participating in the study and their anonymity was protected. A total of 224 university students initially participated in the study. However, data from 6 participants were excluded due to incomplete responses, and the final sample consisted of **218 participants**. Demographic information such as age, gender, department and class level of the participants were analyzed to contribute to the findings of the study. During the survey implementation process, 6 participants stated that they did not want to continue the study without any justification and the data of these participants were excluded from the scope of the

study. Ethical principles were observed and the reliability of the data was increased by allowing the participants to act freely during the study process.

Descriptive statistical methods were used to analyze the data and students' views on active learning processes were evaluated with percentage and frequency distributions. In line with the data obtained, the effects of active learning experiences on students' academic achievement, motivation and communication skills were analyzed and interpreted. The findings obtained from the study provide important clues about the applicability of active learning methods in educational processes.

Findings

When the demographic data of the **218 students** included in the analysis were examined, it was observed that the majority of the participants were female. Of the total participants, 65% were female students and 35% were male students. There were no participants who selected the "Other" option. This distribution may be due to the generally higher proportion of female students in faculties of communication. This difference in gender distribution provides important data for comparing the impact of active learning methods on male and female students. When the departmental distribution of the 218 students who participated in the survey is analyzed, it is seen that the majority of all participants are studying in the Public Relations and Publicity department, constituting approximately 45% of the total participants. This is followed by the Department of Radio, Television and Cinema (30%) and the Department of Journalism (25%). When the class levels of the students participating in the survey are analyzed, it is seen that the highest participation is from 2nd year (40%) and 3rd year (35%) students. While 1st grade students participated at a rate of 15%, the rate of 4th grade students remained at the lowest level with 10%. This distribution shows that active learning methods are experienced more especially in the middle levels of undergraduate education. 2nd and 3rd year students experience active learning processes more, and these methods are used more effectively after the basic courses, when professional specialization and applied courses gain intensity. The relatively low participation of 4th year students can be attributed to the decrease in theoretical courses and the emphasis on applied internships or graduation projects as they approach the graduation process. These results provide important clues as to which stages of the educational process active learning methods are more involved.

All participants in the study indicated that they had encountered active learning methods in at least one course. This finding shows that active learning techniques are widely used in the communication faculty curriculum and that students encounter these methods. Most of the participants indicated that they had taken at least three courses in which active learning methods were applied. However, some students stated that they had experienced active learning in five different courses, proving that the method is widely adopted across communication faculties. Participants indicated that active learning methods were most commonly used in practical courses such as communication theories, public relations campaigns, journalism workshop and radio-television production techniques. This finding shows that active learning methods are more commonly preferred in courses that require practical skills. Participants indicated that group work (70%), discussions (65%) and problem solving (60%) were the most common techniques used in active learning. Although simulations were less preferred among active learning methods (40%), they were found to be an effective method especially in applied courses. The findings show that methods that encourage collaboration and critical thinking are prominent in active learning processes.

When asked about the impact of active learning practices on academic achievement, participants highly evaluated the practices positively. Sixty percent of the participants responded "positive" and 30% responded "very positive". The rate of those who chose "neither positive nor negative" was 8%, while the rate of participants who expressed "negative" opinions was very low (2%). There were no participants who answered "very negative". The data obtained indicate that participants perceived active learning methods as positively associated with their academic development. While the majority of the participants stated that they felt more motivated during the active learning process, 65% of them answered "yes" and 25% answered "definitely yes". The rate of those who chose "neither yes nor no" was 7%, while the rate of participants who expressed negative opinions in terms of motivation was very low (3%). There were no participants who answered "no" or "absolutely no". These findings indicate that participants reported higher levels of interest in the lessons and perceived active learning methods as supportive of their motivation.

The majority of the participants stated that active learning methods contributed positively to their learning processes. While 40% of the respondents answered "5: Very Effective", 35% answered "4", 15% answered "3", only 7% answered "2" and 3% answered "1: No Effect". The low rate of those who chose the "No effect at all" option shows that active learning methods are found effective by the students. Consistent with the previous questions, these data support the perception that active learning processes support students' academic development. In particular, the 75% preference for options 4 and 5 in total shows that active learning methods provide more interaction and participation compared to traditional learning models. However, the presence of a group that finds active learning methods less effective suggests that individual learning and course content shape this perception. Considering the fact that habits cannot be easily abandoned and the previously mentioned disadvantages, it is predicted that the acceptance levels of the participants may increase in these learning styles if these disadvantages are eliminated.

The majority of the study participants stated that they had the opportunity to apply the knowledge they acquired during the active learning process. 35% of the respondents answered "Very often", 40% "Often", 18% "Sometimes". While the rate of those who said "Rarely" remained at a very low level with 5%, there were no participants who chose the "Never" option. These findings show that active learning methods offer important opportunities for students to put theoretical knowledge into practice. In particular, the fact that "Very Often" and "Often" options were preferred by 75% in total reveals that active learning processes are not limited to the stage of acquiring knowledge, but find application areas. However, the presence of a small group who found the opportunity for application less frequently suggests that the course content or the teaching methods used do not offer equal opportunities for application to all students. When the participants were asked whether active learning methods improved their communication skills, 86% of the participants stated that they did, while 14% stated that they did not. These findings suggest that active learning methods play a role in improving communication skills by increasing interaction among students. The widespread use of methods such as group work, discussions and problem solving, which are prominent in the questions asked throughout the survey, is considered to be an effective factor in increasing success. The learning methods applied within the scope of active learning allow students to express their ideas, participate in teamwork and develop effective communication strategies. On the other hand, those who stated that they did not improve their communication skills may not have benefited sufficiently from active learning processes in terms of communication skills due to reasons such as preferring individual learning methods and/or not actively participating in group work.

The majority of the participants emphasized the positive impact of group work on communication skills. In the evaluation made on a five-point scale, 40% of the participants answered "5- Very Effective", 35% answered "4- Effective", 15% of the participants preferred "3- Moderately Effective", 7% answered "2- Slightly Effective" and 3% answered "1- No Effect". These findings reveal that active learning methods improve communication skills by increasing cooperation and interaction among students. Especially when methods that require interaction such as teamwork and discussions are taken into consideration, the data obtained overlap with previous findings. It was thought that the group that found teamwork ineffective in terms of communication may be students who prefer individual learning and/or cannot take an active role due to the dynamics within the group. This suggests that teamwork may not be beneficial for all students and that additional strategies should be developed to increase interaction within the team during the implementation process. It should not be ignored that the strategies to be developed should include activities that students who are prone to individual learning can benefit from.

The participants were asked about the effects of active learning processes on their communication with their friends and 83% of the participants responded that it improved their communication with their friends, while 17% stated that it did not improve their communication with their friends and that it had a neutral effect on their relationships. Participants who thought that active learning methods improved their relationships with their peers emphasized that through teamwork, discussions and problem solving activities, their interactions inside and outside the classroom increased, their teamwork skills improved and they started to express themselves more easily. The findings show that active learning methods support social relations and collaboration processes among students. In addition, students stated that they had the opportunity to think critically and exchange ideas, and therefore their academic achievement increased with social interaction. These data reveal that active learning practices support individual academic development and strengthen interpersonal communication skills. Participants especially see increased participation in lessons, the opportunity to apply what they have learned and the development of communication skills as the most beneficial aspects of active learning. Most of the students stated that these methods made the lessons more interesting, provided permanent learning and improved their critical thinking skills. Students emphasized that they exchanged ideas through group work and discussions, improved their problem solving skills and took an active role in the lessons. Some participants stated that they could easily adapt what they learned in the active learning process to their daily lives and professional fields.

When asked about the adequacy of the promotion of active learning as a method by students with the introduction of active learning practices in educational institutions, the majority of the participants stated that they were informed about the practices, but 60% stated that they would like to receive more information. This shows that students have a high interest in active learning and think that this method should be more involved in educational processes. On the other hand, 40% of the group stated that they did not need more information about active learning practices. This suggests that these participants have acquired sufficient information about active learning methods and their application in the courses they have taken. The data reveals that active learning methods should be introduced to students more comprehensively and that guidance services should be provided.

75% of the participants stated that they think that active learning methods should be applied more in education. These participants emphasized that active learning processes increase student participation, improve public speaking skills, and strengthen critical thinking

and problem solving skills. In addition to this, the participants stated that they developed their skills on the subject through team work and increased interaction in the classroom. However, 25% of the participants stated that they did not support further implementation of active learning methods. The main reason given by these participants was that they were afraid of public speaking and/or sharing their ideas in teams. Another reason was that some students found individual learning more efficient and that active learning methods were not equally effective for all students. The findings indicate that active learning methods are generally perceived positively by students; however, due to individual learning practices and personal preferences, different solutions should be sought for some students and active learning is an area open to improvement.

Participants made various suggestions for active learning methods to be more effective. One of the most frequently emphasized suggestions is to create supportive environments for students who are afraid of public speaking to adapt to this process. Students stated that encouraging individual participation, gradually increasing classroom interaction through small team work, and providing areas where they can practice speaking can be useful. In addition, the need for instructors to play an encouraging role in the active learning process was also revealed. Students drew attention to the importance of the active learning methods used in the courses to be compatible with the course content and emphasized that the applications should be better structured. The need to integrate technological tools more into active learning processes was among the suggestions made by the participants. Especially with the use of digital simulations, interactive materials and online discussion platforms, participants stated that active learning processes can be made more effective. The need for the evaluation process, which is one of the most important areas in education, to be compatible with active learning; the use of presentations, project-based assignments among the evaluation methods is among the expectations of the participants. It was stated that the active learning process should be made more inclusive and accessible for everyone, and the importance of creating a learning environment where timid students can participate comfortably was emphasized.

In general, when the findings obtained as a result of the research are analyzed, most of the participants stated that they found active learning methods positive and that they increased their interest in the lessons. In particular, it was emphasized that practical applications, teamwork and discussion environments support learning. The study participants stated that individual differences should be taken into account in the active learning process and that it may be useful to seek alternative ways of participation for students who have difficulty speaking in the community. Suggestions included providing guidance for students to overcome their reservations in active learning activities and developing methods suitable for different learning styles. It is seen that there is a strong demand among the participants for more widespread and efficient application of active learning methods in the course environment.

Conclusion

This study examined active learning methods, which are frequently used today, through communication faculty students and evaluated the contributions of this method to the educational process in line with the findings obtained. According to the results of the study, it was revealed that participants perceived active learning as being positively associated with their academic achievement, motivation, communication skills and general learning processes. In the study, it was observed that the majority of the participants found active learning techniques more effective than traditional methods. Participants associated this perception with increased interest in the lesson, more lasting learning, and easier transfer of knowledge to practice. Participants reported that group work, discussions and problem-solving activities contributed

to richer learning experiences and increased interaction among students. According to the research data, in lessons conducted with active learning techniques, students show more participation, express their ideas more easily and develop mutual understanding.

The results of the study also showed that active learning methods had positive effects on students in terms of communication skills. These results are in direct parallel with the studies in the literature. 86% of the participants stated that active learning methods improved their communication skills and 65% stated that they changed their interactions with their classmates positively. Group work, collaborative projects, and in-class discussions, which are all part of active learning methods, allow students to express their ideas openly, listen to different opinions, and find common solutions. This not only supports the development of social skills but also lays the foundations for the communication competencies needed in professional life after graduation. Perceived improvements in communication skills were associated with more effective teamwork and collaborative learning experiences. However, the study also revealed that active learning may not be equally effective for all students. In particular, students who prefer individual learning and/or who are afraid of public speaking may have difficulties during the active learning process. This situation shows that learning environments should be made more flexible and inclusive. It is important to implement active learning methods by taking into account individual differences in order to involve all students in the process.

The contribution of active learning methods to academic achievement is related to the direct involvement of students in the process. 83% of the participants stated that these methods improved their academic performance. This shows that learning by exploring knowledge enables students to approach subjects more deeply and develop critical thinking skills. Students' active participation in the learning process also increases the long-term retention and usability of the information learned. In the motivation dimension, it was observed that active learning techniques increased students' interest in the lesson and reduced distraction. 75% of the students who participated in the study stated that they felt more motivated during active learning processes. This finding reveals that students assume more responsibility and develop a more intrinsic commitment to the learning process when they are actively involved in the process rather than merely passively exposed to information.

Another noteworthy finding of the research is the difficulties students have in putting into practice the knowledge they have acquired through active learning. While only 40% of the participants stated that they frequently had the opportunity to apply what they had learned, a significant number of them stated that this opportunity occurred "sometimes" or "rarely". This finding suggests that for active learning to be effective, application areas should be diversified. Course environments supported by activities such as applied course content, case studies, simulations and projects will make it possible to reinforce knowledge in practice.

The analysis of students' general perceptions of active learning indicated a widespread agreement that this approach should be more extensively integrated into the educational system. 82% of the participants think that more frequent use of active learning techniques would be beneficial. However, it was also emphasized that in order for this process to be carried out efficiently, instructors need to plan effectively, manage time and establish healthy communication with students. Some participants stated that there was occasional loss of efficiency due to group cohesion problems and deficiencies in process management. At this point, it becomes clear that instructors should manage the process in a more structured and guidance-based manner.

In conclusion, active learning methods are perceived by students as offering a holistic approach that supports their academic, social and emotional development. Through these methods, students not only access information, but also construct, apply and analyze this information. In order to implement active learning effectively, course content should be aligned with this approach, instructors should have knowledge and skills in the method, learning environments should be designed in a way that is conducive to implementation, and student feedback should be regularly evaluated. When these conditions are met, active learning techniques may function as an effective learning mode that fosters not only individual achievement, but also societal and professional competencies.

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